

Optimizing QoE for Virtual Reality Games on Mobile Edge Networks

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Abstract

In this paper, we explore delivering mobile edge Virtual Reality (VR) gaming services with comprehensive and satisfactory Quality of Experience (QoE) across a distributed edge network. Our goal is to meet the QoE needs of all users, addressing both latency and visual considerations. However, the unique characteristics of edge-assisted mobile VR gaming distinguish our challenge from other distributed service provisioning issues. We introduce and address the challenge of provisioning QoE-centric mobile VR gaming services within a distributed edge environment by systematically capturing the unique attributes of mobile VR games. We demonstrate that this challenge can be formulated as a Mixed-Integer Quadratically Constrained Quadratic Programming (MIQCQP) problem. While mobile edge computing holds promise for mobile VR gaming, existing studies often overlook the need to deliver satisfactory QoE to a large user base. Our paper focuses on delivering QoE-centric edge-assisted mobile VR gaming services to multiple users, comprehensively addressing visual and latency concerns.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, Virtual Reality (VR) technology has experienced significant growth, offering users immersive and interactive experiences in virtual environments. This surge in popularity has led to the widespread adoption of various VR-assisted services and applications, providing users with more engaging and immersive visual experiences compared to traditional 2D video formats [1], [2].

To provide users with a satisfying experience, VR systems need to meet two critical criteria [3]–[5]: minimizing interactive latency and delivering high-fidelity visual rendering. Ensuring minimal interactive latency enhances responsiveness, reducing the potential dizziness or user discomfort, while meeting high-quality visual standards enriches the immersive nature of the VR experience.

As an emerging technique, edge-assisted mobile VR aims to enhance user experience through Quality of Experience (QoE) improvements, achieved by harnessing the computational resources of edge cloudlets [3], [6]–[10]. This addresses the pressing demand for seamless and immersive VR environments. For instance, [8], [9] render the entire frame on the edge. While in [10] explores feasibility of high-quality mobile VR. In [7] render the frames considering both the Field of View (FoV) and saliency. However, while the previous studies explore various aspects of VR, they do focus on a single scenario.

Within the realm of VR 360-degree video streaming services, several studies [6], [7], [11]–[13] have concentrated on the provisioning of mobile-oriented platforms. These services entail the pre-rendering and caching of panoramic content at the edge, facilitating smoother streaming experiences for users on mobile devices. Additionally, significant attention has been directed towards enhancing the efficiency and quality of mobile 360-degree video streaming services. However, while studies on multi-user 360 video streaming systems provide valuable insights, they might not directly apply to mobile VR game scenarios due to differences in user behavior, interaction dynamics, and the requirements of the system. The design considerations and mechanisms for reducing data transmission rates would need to be tailored to the specific characteristics and demands of mobile VR gaming.

In Figure 1 visually represents a distributed mobile VR gaming system, leveraging edge computing to support multiple users. As illustrated, the VR game is deployed across various mobile edges and devices by the provider. Unlike focusing solely on individual user experience requirements, the emphasis is on optimizing the collective quality of experience (QoE) for all users. Within the constraints of edge computing resources, the central challenge involves devising a service provisioning strategy for mobile VR gaming. This entails making informed decisions regarding rendering computation allocation and resource distribution to ensure optimal performance and a seamless gaming experience for each user.

This work explores the challenge of providing high-quality mobile edge VR game services within a distributed edge network. The objective is to meet the quality of experience (QoE) needs of users, considering both latency and visual aspects. The unique characteristics of edge-assisted mobile VR gaming present distinct challenges:

1. Numerous Independent Objects: In VR gaming environments, such as those featuring avatars or weapons, every object operates through its rendering pipeline, intensifying the intricacy of determining their placements. In modern VR game engines like Unity3D or Unreal Engine 4, objects are equipped with distinct rendering pipelines, allowing them to be rendered autonomously. This results in a considerable expansion of the search space for making object placement decisions.

Figure 1: An illustrative overview showcasing the intricate network and computing infrastructure of a distributed edge-assisted mobile VR gaming system, highlighting its components, connectivity, and interactions.

2. Diverse Rendering Levels: VR/3D games provide a range of rendering options to cater to different visual QoE needs, which adds complexity to decision-making due to the inclusion of multiple rendering level choices.

3. Tight End-to-End Delay Requirement: The end-to-end delay in mobile VR games comprises rendering and encoding delay, as well as transmission delay, as illustrated in Figure 2. This delay is crucial for maintaining interactivity, with VR games typically requiring low delay, often less than 15 milliseconds. Traditional linear programming frameworks are ill-suited for addressing these delay constraints.

4. High Bandwidth Usage: Balancing the significant bandwidth consumption in mobile VR games, attributed to their high visual demands, poses a challenge. This demand often results in higher rendering levels and consequently, increased delay. Managing these conflicting quality of experience (QoE) requirements emerges as a critical challenge in edge-assisted mobile VR gaming systems.

In this paper, we investigate delivering high-quality mobile edge VR gaming across a distributed network. We address unique challenges in providing QoE-centric services, formulated as a MIQCQP problem. Our focus is on meeting users' QoE needs, considering both latency and visual aspects.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

A. Problem Definition

Let's examine a distributed edge system, where the collection of edges is represented by $\mathcal{D} := \{1, 2, \dots, D\}$. An expression is given $\forall d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}$, this ensures that each decision d encompasses both local edge and distributed placement possibilities, offering flexibility in object allocation strategies for user i 's object j . The variable d represents the decision for placing an object, which can either be take values from the set $\{0\}$ for local execution edge or chosen from the set \mathcal{D} representing alternative placement options in distributed edge clouds. The edge servers or access points are co-located with the first network gateways (such as WiFi access points and 4G/5G base stations) of the end users. It is assumed that the Virtual Reality (VR) game has been deployed both on the edges and on the mobile devices. The set of mobile VR game users is denoted as $\mathcal{I} := \{1, 2, \dots, I\}$. The set of objects within the viewpoint of user i 's is represented as \mathcal{J}_i . The VR game offers various rendering levels for each object, and the collection of these available rendering levels is indicated by $\mathcal{L} := \{1, 2, \dots, L\}$.

Figure 2: Latencies observed in mobile VR gaming with support from edge computing, illustrating the time delays between user interactions and corresponding responses within the virtual environment.

B. Modeling the Binary Variable

We define $x_{i,j,d} \in \{0, 1\}$ as a binary variable, where $\forall i \in \mathcal{I}, \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_i$, and $\forall d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}$. It represents the decision regarding the placement of object j for user i . When $d = 0$, it indicates local execution. Therefore, if $x_{i,j,d} = 1$, it denotes that object j for user i is displayed on edge d , while $x_{i,j,d} = 0$ implies that object j for user i is not displayed on edge d when $d \in \mathcal{D}$. Similarly, $x_{i,j,0} = 1$ suggests that object j for user i is displayed locally edge, whereas $x_{i,j,0} = 0$ implies otherwise. The binary variable $x_{i,j,d} \in \{0, 1\}$ indicates whether is utilized in the d^{th} position. If $x_{i,j,d} = 1$, it denotes that it is employed in the d^{th} position, while $x_{i,j,d} = 0$ implies otherwise. For $x_{i,j,d}$, these binary variables are used to model the connection constraint for each object j within user i 's panorama to precisely connect to the edge. Therefore, the connection constraint is:

$$\sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} x_{i,j,d} = 1, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}, \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_i. \quad (1)$$

This constraint ensures that for each object j within the user i 's panorama view, the sum of the binary variables $\sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} x_{i,j,d}$ over all bitrate levels d (including level 0) is equal to 1. This implies that exactly one bitrate level is chosen for the uplink transmission for each object in the panorama.

C. Modeling the QoE Objective

The users' QoE in visual panorama experiences depends on the perceived importance of objects, denoted by $w_{i,j}$ for user i and object j . We assume $\sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} w_{i,j} = 1$. We adopt a linear QoE model for bitrate [7], [11], [12], [14], suitable for high-bitrate mobile VR gaming, approximating more complex models like logarithmic and PSNR/SSIM. Previous studies used bitrates from 8Mbps to 48Mbps [15], fixed at 36Mbps [16], and 8Mbps to 32Mbps in our study. Our findings show that the linear model adequately approximates complex QoE models with errors below 5.8% for logarithmic and 2.6% for PSNR. Given μ as the bitrate for rendering level 1, the expected QoE for user i , as specified in [17], can be defined as follows:

$$QoE_i = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} w_{i,j} \cdot q(\mu, l_{i,j}), \forall i \in \mathcal{I}, \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_i, \quad (2)$$

where the function $q()$ is a mapping function, which maps the bitrate to the quality perceived by the user. $l_{i,j}$ the rendering level for object j of user i and $w_{i,j}$ the visual QoE weight or object j of user i . In the context of VR, "rendering level" typically refers to the quality and complexity of the graphical rendering or graphics rendering of the virtual environment. Rendering is the process of generating the images that users see in the VR headset, and the rendering level is a measure of the visual fidelity and detail in those images.

D. Rendering and Encoding Delay Constraint

In the context of VR gaming, rendering involves the generation of a digital image that can be displayed on the screen. This process relies on 3D models and various rendering parameters such as lighting, materials, textures, and rendering complexity. Our experiments demonstrate a direct correlation between rendering and encoding time and rendering complexity. This observation aligns with similar experiments conducted in [18], [19], which indicate that rendering and encoding time exhibit a linear relationship with rendering precision. Consequently, we represent rendering and encoding time as a linear function of rendering complexity. The interaction among objects is represented by the ‘dilation factor’, as mentioned in [20]. According to [20], the extension of computational speed is directly proportional to the workload, where the workload is defined as the number of objects in our specific context. We use $\alpha_{d,1}, \forall d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}$ to denote the dilation factor.

Consider $h_{i,j,d}$ as the combined rendering and encoding time for object j of user i at location d , where $\forall d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}$, and there is no contention in terms of CPU cycles. Consequently, the rendering time for object j of user i at location d , where $\forall d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}$, can be expressed as follows:

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} \sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} \alpha_{d,1} \cdot l_{i,j} \cdot h_{i,j,d}. \quad (3)$$

Note that $h_{i,j,d}$ describes the computational time for a virtual object for a user at a specific location within a virtual or augmented reality context, rather than explicitly referring to a camera.

E. Transmission Delay Constraint

The exchange of data between the edge and the mobile device is crucial for rendering objects on the edge side. This data exchange is termed as transmission delay, which comprises two key components: the time taken for the mobile device to upload data to the edge (uploading time) and the time for the edge to send back rendered data to the mobile device (downloading time). Each component consists of two parts: the time required for data transmission (sending time) and the time taken for data to travel from one end to the other (propagation time) [8]–[10].

Sending Time: The superficial area, which represents the visible surface area, of object j for user i is denoted as $s_{i,j}$. In the context of this study, the resolution ratio of an object refers to the number of pixels per unit area and per frame level after rendering, denoted by $r_{i,j}$ for object j belonging to user i , while q_i denotes the frame rate of user i . The bitrate per pixel of object j for user i , $p_{i,j}$, corresponds to the encoding rate of the encoding algorithm applied. Throughout our investigation, we maintain a fixed frame rate (60fps in our experiments) and a consistent compression ratio. Notably, the frame rate remains constant throughout a gaming session, while q_i may vary to accommodate different frame rate settings in various gaming sessions. Consequently, the video size before compression and the bitrate typically exhibit a linear relationship. Thus, the compressed data size of object j for user i is calculated as $l_{i,j} \cdot s_{i,j} \cdot r_{i,j} \cdot q_i \cdot p_{i,j}$, and the available bandwidth for object j of user i is denoted as $l_{i,j} \cdot \mu$. This concept of superficial area aids in understanding the visible surfaces and their impact on data processing and transmission within the virtual environment. In the process of rendering the object, the transmission time can be determined by dividing the data size by the available bandwidth, as expressed by the following constraint:

$$\frac{l_{i,j} \cdot s_{i,j} \cdot r_{i,j} \cdot q_i \cdot p_{i,j}}{l_{i,j} \mu} = \frac{s_{i,j} \cdot r_{i,j} \cdot q_i \cdot p_{i,j}}{\mu}, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}, \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_i. \quad (4)$$

Propagation Time: In mobile VR gaming latency, understanding propagation time is crucial, as it encompasses the transmission duration discussed earlier. Propagation time primarily depends on the transmission medium between the edge and the mobile device. Denoted as $\lambda_{i,d}$, the propagation time from location d , $\forall d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}$, to user i is of utmost importance. To ensure precise display of each object at a specific location, the propagation time for object j of user i is expressed as follows:

$$\sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} \lambda_{i,d} \cdot x_{i,j,d}, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}, \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_i, \quad (5)$$

where, $x_{i,j,d}$ might represent a binary variable associated with the propagation of uplink data for object j of user i .

Transmission Delay: Considering the preceding discussion, we can model the transmission delay for object j of user i , encompassing scenarios where the object is rendered locally, as follows:

$$\sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} \lambda_{i,d} \cdot x_{i,j,d} + \frac{s_{i,j} \cdot r_{i,j} \cdot q_i \cdot p_{i,j}}{\mu}, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}, \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_i. \quad (6)$$

F. End-to-End Delay Constraint

Suppose τ represents the maximum tolerable end-to-end (E2E) delay, commonly set to 50 ms for VR to ensure a high-quality user experience in terms of QoE, Quality of Perception (QoP), and Quality of Demand (QoD). Given that all objects can render and transmit simultaneously, a user's E2E delay is determined by the maximum delay among all objects associated with that user. The overall end-to-end latency model comprises rendering and encoding delays, along with transmission and reception delays. Considering the mobile device as the rendering and encoding entity, the latency model. Therefore, the E2E delay constraint can be expressed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} \sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} \alpha_{d,1} \cdot l_{i,j} \cdot h_{i,j,d} + \sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} \lambda_{i,d} + \\ & \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} \sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} \alpha_{d,2} \cdot \frac{s_{i,j} \cdot r_{i,j} \cdot q_i \cdot p_{i,j}}{\mu} \leq \tau, \\ & \forall i \in \mathcal{I}, \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_i, \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where we introduce a second dilation factor $\alpha_{d,2}$, emphasizing the critical importance of understanding the linear relationship between computation speed and workload for deciphering the performance dynamics of VR systems, especially in managing intricate virtual environments with fluctuating numbers of objects or elements requiring real-time processing.

G. Bandwidth Modeling Constraint

The capacity of the edge network is constrained due to its limited bandwidth. Given that the edge server is positioned at the initial network gateway for end users, the bottleneck within the edge network could stem from either the outgoing bandwidth at the edge server or the link bandwidth connecting the edge and the local mobile device. This bandwidth limitation affects data flow in both directions. Let's denote B_d , where $d \in \mathcal{D}$, as the outgoing bandwidth of edge d . Similarly, let $b_{d,i}$, with $i \in \mathcal{I}$ and $d \in \mathcal{D}$, represent the respective link bandwidths between edge d and user i . Consequently, the channel's bandwidth constraint begins with the following constraints:

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} \mu \cdot l_{i,j} \cdot x_{i,j,d} \leq B_d, \quad \forall d \in \mathcal{D}, \quad (8)$$

$$\sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} \mu \cdot l_{i,j} \cdot x_{i,j,d} \leq b_{d,i}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I}, \forall d \in \mathcal{D}, \quad (9)$$

where the expression $\sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} \mu \cdot l_{i,j} \cdot x_{i,j,d}$ denotes the aggregate bandwidth requirements of all objects originating from each user on edge d .

III. PROBLEM FORMULATION

In the previous section, we conceptualized the optimization objective as meeting visual requirements to accommodate a range of user interests while considering constraints such as delay, bandwidth, and placement within the model. Consequently, the problem involves incorporating delay constraints (7) and bandwidth constraints (8) and (9), along with binary constraints referred to as 'placement constraints' (1), which dictate the positioning of tasks or services within the infrastructure. As quadratic-constrained problems often do not include equation constraints, it becomes essential to convert these equation constraints into inequalities to enable the attainment of solutions.

As each variable $x_{i,j,d}$ takes values in the set $\{0, 1\}$ for all $i \in \mathcal{I}$, $j \in \mathcal{J}_i$, and $d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}$, the summation $\sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} x_{i,j,d}$ should result in a value within the set $\{0, 1, 2, \dots, D\}$, where D represents the size of set \mathcal{D} . Consequently, the equation $\sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} x_{i,j,d} = 1$ is equivalent to the inequality constraints $\sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} x_{i,j,d} \leq 1$ and $\sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} x_{i,j,d} \neq 0$. On the contrary, when $\sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} x_{i,j,d} = 0$, it signifies that object j of user i is not rendered anywhere, resulting in the minimal visual QoE for object j of user i (i.e., the visual QoE is 0). Therefore, the equation constraint $\sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} x_{i,j,d} = 1$ can be replaced with the inequality constraint $\sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} x_{i,j,d} \leq 1$. Additionally, by incorporating $\sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} x_{i,j,d}$ into the objective function and maximizing it, the sum of the placement decisions automatically avoids being 0. Therefore, the placement constraint is assured within the framework of an inequality.

To refine the algorithmic framework, we employ a transformation for all variables to 0-1 indicator variables. Specifically, we substitute each rendering level selection variable $l_{i,j} \in \mathcal{L}$, $\forall i \in \mathcal{I}$, $\forall j \in \mathcal{J}_i$ with a set of rendering level indicator variables $l_{i,j,v} \in \{0, 1\}$, $\forall i \in \mathcal{I}$, $\forall j \in \mathcal{J}_i$, $\forall \psi \in \mathcal{L}$.

Here ψ indicates the rendering level, and $l_{i,j,\psi}$ signifies whether object j of user i is rendered at level ψ . Each rendering level ψ can be viewed as a factor that scales the importance or significance of the rendering status $l_{i,j,\psi}$ in the overall rendering

process. As each object is rendered with precisely one rendering level, $\sum_{\psi \in \mathcal{L}} l_{i,j,\psi} = 1$. To maximize the visual Quality of Experience (QoE), it follows that $l_{i,j,\psi}$ cannot all be 0. Therefore, we converted the equation constraint $\sum_{\psi \in \mathcal{L}} l_{i,j,\psi} = 1$ to the inequality constraint $\sum_{v \in \mathcal{L}} l_{i,j,\psi} \leq 1$. As a result, we define the QoE-oriented VR game service within a distributed edge network as:

$$\max. \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} w_{i,j} \cdot \lambda \cdot \sum_{\psi \in \mathcal{L}} l_{i,j,\psi} \cdot \sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} x_{i,j,d} \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{s.t.} \quad & \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} \sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} \alpha_{d,1} \cdot l_{i,j} \cdot h_{i,j,d} + \sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} \lambda_{i,j}, \\ & + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} \sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} \alpha_{d,2} \cdot \frac{s_{i,j} \cdot r_{i,j} \cdot q_i \cdot p_{i,j}}{\mu} \leq \tau, \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

$$\forall i \in \mathcal{I}, \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_i,$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} \mu \cdot x_{i,j,d} \cdot \left(\sum_{\psi \in \mathcal{L}} l_{i,j,\psi} \right) \leq B_d, \quad \forall d \in \mathcal{D}, \quad (12)$$

$$\mu \cdot \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} \left(\sum_{\psi \in \mathcal{L}} l_{i,j,\psi} \right) \cdot x_{i,j,d} \leq b_{d,i}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I}, \forall d \in \mathcal{D}, \quad (13)$$

$$\sum_{d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}} x_{i,j,d} \leq 1, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I}, \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_i, \quad (14)$$

$$\sum_{\psi \in \mathcal{L}} l_{i,j,\psi} \leq 1, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I}, \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_i, \quad (15)$$

$$x_{i,j,d} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I}, \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_i, \forall d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D},$$

$$l_{i,j,\psi} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I}, \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_i, \forall \psi \in \mathcal{L}.$$

The aim of addressing Problem (10) - (15) is to maximize the overall visual QoE for all users, while adhering to constraints related to E2E delay, object placement, and bandwidth. In contrast to prior studies, which primarily focused on meeting delay requirements in distributed mobile edge VR gaming [21]–[23], our approach stands out by considering a holistic QoE that incorporates both delay and visual considerations. The problem involves two types of variables: object placement variables ($x_{i,j,d} \in \{0, 1\}$, $\forall i \in \mathcal{I}$, $\forall j \in \mathcal{J}_i$, $\forall d \in \{0\} \cup \mathcal{D}$) and rendering level selection variables ($l_{i,j,\psi} \in \{0, 1\}$, $\forall i \in \mathcal{I}$, $\forall j \in \mathcal{J}_i$, $\forall \psi \in \mathcal{L}$).

Analyzing Problem (10), it becomes evident that the objective function and Constraints (11), (12) and (13) all involve the multiplication of two distinct variable types. Consequently, the nature of the problem is identified as a Mixed-Integer Quadratically Constrained Quadratic Programming (MIQCQP) problem with 0-1 integer variables.

Convergence Performance: The inherent non-convexity of the general MIQCQP problem precludes the application of conventional methods reliant on strong convergence properties. However, an alternative avenue emerges through the utilization of the weak convergence property. This property stipulates that if an algorithm converges for the non-convex problem, it will converge to a Karush-Kuhn-Tucker (KKT) point. Moreover, as demonstrated, the MIQCQP problem can be readily reformulated as a QP problem for solution, highlighting a pivotal linkage between MIQCQP and QP. By iteratively updating the primal and dual variables, the algorithm converges to a KKT point, as demonstrated through the derivation of the KKT conditions. As the iteration index approaches infinity, both the primal and dual variables converge, ultimately satisfying the KKT conditions. This convergence property provides theoretical support for the reliability of the algorithm in finding meaningful solutions to the non-convex MIQCQP problem, showcasing the algorithm's ability to navigate the complexities of non-convex optimization challenges and converge to KKT points, which represent critical points of the optimization problem. The proof of weak convergence in Appendix A supports the algorithm's reliability in solving the non-convex MIQCQP problem.

IV. RESULTS

In this section, we present the results of our comprehensive analysis on the factors influencing QoE in VR gaming environments. We explore three key aspects: α_1 , α_2 , and τ , which represent critical parameters affecting the performance and user satisfaction in VR gaming systems. Subsequently, we investigate the relationship between the number of users and the Mbps throughput, providing insights into the scalability and network requirements necessary to support optimal VR experiences. Additionally, we present the visual ratio of the QoE weights in Figure 5, offering insights into the prioritization of various QoE metrics and their significance in enhancing overall gaming immersion.

Figure 3: 3D Plot of τ vs. α_1 and α_2

A. Dilation Factor ($\alpha_{1\vee 2}$) and Max. Tolerable E2E delay (τ)

In the context of the VR system, the dilation factors $\alpha_1 \vee \alpha_2$ play pivotal roles in shaping the temporal and spatial characteristics of data processing and transmission, directly impacting the E2E delay. These factors represent the degree of expansion applied to different components within the system, influencing the speed and efficiency of data handling.

As we see in Figure 3, α_1 and α_2 increase, indicating greater levels of dilation, the system may require additional processing time or bandwidth to handle the expanded data streams effectively. Consequently, the maximum tolerable E2E delay τ tends to increase linearly with the dilation factors.

This observed linear relationship underscores the inherent trade-offs between processing complexity, spatial resolution, and E2E latency within the VR environment. While higher dilation factors may enhance image quality or spatial detail, they also introduce additional processing overhead and potential delays in delivering content to the user.

Optimizing the dilation factors involves striking a balance between achieving the desired visual fidelity and maintaining acceptable levels of E2E delay. By understanding the linear relationship between dilation factors and E2E delay, system designers can make informed decisions to fine-tune system parameters and enhance the overall user experience in the VR environment.

B. Number of Users vs Mbps

The Figure 4 depicts results where the bandwidth available to users ranges from 10 Mbps through 90 Mbps. The x-axis represents the number of users, ranging from 1 to 10, while the y-axis indicates resulting bandwidth values ranging from approximately 2 Mbps to 153 Mbps. The data was transformed into a cubic format to model the relationship between user count and bandwidth demand due to their ability to accurately capture nonlinear behavior in the data. The bars points highlight the increasing demands on network resources as the user count rises, crucial for effective network planning and resource management to ensure optimal performance and Quality of Service (QoS). Interestingly, the analysis suggests a somewhat linear increase in bandwidth demand as user count grows, reflecting practical implications despite the underlying nature of the data.

This analysis of bandwidth allocation underscores the critical role of Quality of QoS considerations in network planning and resource management for VR environments. While bandwidth allocation is essential for supporting immersive VR experiences, E2E delay constraints also play a pivotal role in ensuring optimal user satisfaction. E2E delay constraints, represented by the maximum tolerable delay denoted as τ , impose significant limitations on system performance. They encompass various latency factors, including rendering, encoding, transmission, and reception delays. Our study integrates these constraints into the analysis to maintain seamless VR experiences and uphold stringent QoS standards.

Figure 4: Bandwidth demand vs number of users.

The introduction of the dilation factor, $\alpha_{d,1}$ and $\alpha_{d,2}$, emphasizes the importance of understanding the linear relationship between computation speed and workload in VR systems. This factor further underscores the need for efficient resource allocation and management to mitigate delays and optimize system performance. The increasing demands on network resources, as depicted by the results, highlight the necessity for effective network planning and resource management strategies. By addressing bandwidth allocation and E2E delay constraints, organizations can enhance overall performance and quality of service in VR environments, thereby improving user satisfaction and immersive experiences (QoE).

C. QoE Weights

The Figure 5 graphical representation provides an insightful glimpse into the allocation of visual QoE weights among diverse object types within the system. Each bar in the graph delineates the proportion of visual QoE weight assigned to a specific object type, with normalization ensuring a cumulative total of 100%. The visualization of the rendering levels underscores the profound influence of visual QoE weights on system dynamics. It emphasizes the critical role these weights play in shaping the overall user experience and system performance. However, it's essential to acknowledge that the precise allocation of visual QoE weights constitutes a distinct consideration that falls beyond the scope of this study.

Within this distribution, the 'First Level' of object emerges as the primary contributor to the overall visual experience, accounting for 40% of the total visual QoE. Following closely, the 'Second Level' significantly impacts visual QoE with a contribution of 30%. Comparatively, the 'Third Level' and 'Fourth type' represent smaller proportions of the total visual QoE weight, accounting for 20% and 10%, respectively.

This distribution underscores the varying degrees of importance attributed to different object types in enhancing the overall visual experience within the system. Consequently, insights derived from this analysis can guide strategic decisions regarding

Figure 5: QoE Weights: A Visual Aid. We assumed a ratio of 4:3:2:1. Since $\sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_i} w_{i,j} = 1$, it follows that the combined product of each object type's ratio, the total number of users I , and the weight of each object type equals 1. Let's designate the visual QoE weight of the least significant object type as w . Thus, the equation becomes: $5\% \cdot I \cdot 4 \cdot w + 10\% \cdot I \cdot 3 \cdot w + 35\% \cdot I \cdot 2 \cdot w + 50\% \cdot I \cdot w = 1$. Therefore, $w = \frac{10}{17 \cdot I}$. Consequently, the visual QoE weights for the four object types are calculated as follows: $\frac{40}{17 \cdot I}$, $\frac{30}{17 \cdot I}$, $\frac{20}{17 \cdot I}$, and $\frac{10}{17 \cdot I}$, respectively.

resource allocation and optimization efforts. Prioritizing objects with higher visual QoE weights holds the potential to enhance user satisfaction and system efficiency.

V. CONCLUSION

In our paper, we analyze the relationship between the number of users and bandwidth allocation, highlighting the increasing demands on network resources and the critical importance of maintaining stringent QoS standards for seamless VR experiences. Additionally, we examine the distribution of visual QoE among object types, identifying opportunities for strategic resource allocation. The limited bandwidth capacity of the edge network poses constraints on data flow, potentially leading to bottlenecks. These limitations can arise from either the outgoing bandwidth at the edge server or the link bandwidth connecting the edge and the local mobile device. Our findings underscore the necessity of informed resource management to enhance VR performance and user satisfaction, including aspects such as Quality of Perception and Quality of Demand. This paper focuses on delivering high-quality mobile edge VR gaming across a distributed network, addressing unique challenges in providing QoE-centric services formulated as an MIQCQP problem. Our primary goal is to ensure users' QoE by carefully managing bandwidth resources from both user devices and within the mobile edge infrastructure, addressing latency concerns, and optimizing visual quality.

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APPENDIX A: PROOF OF THEOREM 1

Proof: The MIQCQP problem can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{maximize} && f(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{x}^T \mathbf{A}_0 \mathbf{x} + 2\mathbf{b}_0^T \mathbf{x} + c_0 \\ & \text{subject to} && \mathbf{x}^T \mathbf{A}_s \mathbf{x} + 2\mathbf{b}_s^T \mathbf{x} + c_s \leq 0, \quad \forall s \in \{1, \dots, m\}, \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

where the objective function $f(\mathbf{x})$ is a quadratic function of \mathbf{x} with the coefficient matrix \mathbf{A}_0 and the linear term \mathbf{b}_0 , along with a constant term c_0 . The constraints are quadratic inequality constraints, each with its own coefficient matrix \mathbf{A}_s , linear term \mathbf{b}_s , and constant term c_s . These constraints are imposed $\forall s \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, which represents the indices of the constraints. By embedding all the inequality constraints and range constraints within the objective function, we can observe that \mathbf{y} and z_1, \dots, z_m effectively represent the variables of the optimization problem in (10) to (15).

The corresponding algorithm iteration is described as follows:

Updating \mathbf{y}^{k+1} :

$$\mathbf{y}^{k+1} = (\mathbf{A}_0 + m\rho\mathbf{I})^{-1} [\rho(\mathbf{z}_s^k + \boldsymbol{\mu}_s^k) - \mathbf{b}_0], \quad (17)$$

where (17) updates \mathbf{y}^{k+1} in the optimization algorithm. It calculates the new value of \mathbf{y}^{k+1} based on the previous values of \mathbf{z}_s^k and $\boldsymbol{\mu}_s^k$, using the matrices \mathbf{A}_0 and \mathbf{b}_0 . This update ensures that \mathbf{y}^{k+1} satisfies the optimization problem, considering the influence of the dual variables $\boldsymbol{\mu}_s^k$ and the objective function represented by \mathbf{A}_0 and \mathbf{b}_0 .

Updating \mathbf{z}^{k+1} :

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{z}^{k+1} &= \operatorname{argmax} \|\mathbf{z}_s - \mathbf{y}^{k+1} - \boldsymbol{\mu}_s^k\|^2 \\ \text{s.t.} &: \mathbf{x}^T \mathbf{A}_s \mathbf{x} + 2\mathbf{b}_s^T \mathbf{x} + c_s \leq 0, \quad \forall s \in \{1, \dots, m\}, \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

where this step involves updating \mathbf{z}_s^{k+1} in the algorithm. \mathbf{z}_s^{k+1} is optimized to minimize the squared Euclidean distance between \mathbf{z}_s , \mathbf{y}^{k+1} , and $\boldsymbol{\mu}_s^k$, while ensuring compliance with the quadratic inequality constraints for all s .

Updating $\boldsymbol{\mu}_s^{k+1}$:

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_s^{k+1} = \boldsymbol{\mu}_s^k + \mathbf{y}^{k+1} - \mathbf{z}_s^{k+1}, \quad \forall s \in \{1, \dots, m\}, \quad (20)$$

where (20) describes the update process for each $\boldsymbol{\mu}_s^{k+1}$ in the algorithm. It calculates the new value of $\boldsymbol{\mu}_s^{k+1}$ by adding the difference between \mathbf{y}^{k+1} and \mathbf{z}_s^{k+1} to the previous value of $\boldsymbol{\mu}_s^k$. This update is applied to $\forall s \in \{1, \dots, m\}$.

Therefore, $\forall s \in \{1, \dots, m\}$,

$$\mathbf{A}_0 \mathbf{y}^{k+1} + m\rho \mathbf{y}^{k+1} = \rho(\mathbf{z}_s^k + \boldsymbol{\mu}_s^k) - \mathbf{b}_0, \quad (21)$$

$$\mathbf{z}^{k+1} = \operatorname{argmax} \|\mathbf{z}_s - \mathbf{y}^{k+1} - \boldsymbol{\mu}_s^k\|^2, \quad (22)$$

$$\exists \eta_s^{k+1} \geq 0, \text{ s.t.: } \boldsymbol{\mu}_s^k + \eta_s^{k+1} (\mathbf{A}_s \mathbf{z}_s^{k+1} + \mathbf{b}_s) = 0, \quad (23)$$

where (21) computes the updated value of \mathbf{y}^{k+1} based on the previous values of \mathbf{z}_s^k and $\boldsymbol{\mu}_s^k$. In (22) is determined \mathbf{z}_s^{k+1} by maximizing the squared distance between \mathbf{z}_s , \mathbf{y}^{k+1} , and $\boldsymbol{\mu}_s^k$. The introduction of Lagrange multipliers η_s^{k+1} ensures that the updated $\boldsymbol{\mu}_s^{k+1}$ values adhere to the constraints, as specified in (23). These equations collectively drive the iterative update process of the optimization algorithm, aiming for convergence towards a solution that simultaneously satisfies the optimization problem and its constraints.

Since

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_s^{k+1} = \boldsymbol{\mu}_s^k + \mathbf{y}^{k+1} - \mathbf{z}_s^{k+1}, \quad \forall s \in \{1, \dots, m\}, \quad (24)$$

and

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow +\infty} (\mathbf{z}_s^k - \mathbf{y}^k) = 0, \quad \forall s \in \{1, \dots, m\}, \quad (25)$$

we have,

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow +\infty} (\boldsymbol{\mu}_s^{k+1} - \boldsymbol{\mu}_s^k) = 0, \quad \forall s \in \{1, \dots, m\}, \quad (26)$$

where (24) represents the iterative update for the dual variable $\boldsymbol{\mu}_s$ in the optimization algorithm. It computes the new value of $\boldsymbol{\mu}_s^{k+1}$ by adding the difference between \mathbf{y}^{k+1} and \mathbf{z}_s^{k+1} to the previous value of $\boldsymbol{\mu}_s^k$. This update is applied to $\forall s \in \{1, \dots, m\}$,

ensuring that each dual variable is appropriately adjusted based on the current values of \mathbf{y} and \mathbf{z} . The limit expression in (25) indicates that as the iteration index k approaches infinity, the difference between \mathbf{z}_s^k and \mathbf{y}^k tends to zero $\forall s \in \{1, \dots, m\}$. This suggests that the sequences \mathbf{z}_s^k and \mathbf{y}^k converge to the same value as k becomes very large, implying potential convergence of the optimization algorithm. Similarly, the limit expression (26) indicates that as k tends to infinity, the difference between consecutive iterations of $\boldsymbol{\mu}_s$ converges to zero $\forall s \in \{1, \dots, m\}$. This suggests that the sequence $\boldsymbol{\mu}_s^k$ converges to a stable value as the algorithm progresses, potentially indicating convergence of the dual variables.

Therefore, when $k \rightarrow +\infty$,

$$\mathbf{A}_0 \mathbf{y}^{k+1} + m \rho \mathbf{y}^{k+1} = \rho [\mathbf{y}^k - \eta_s^{k+1} (\mathbf{A}_s \mathbf{y}^{k+1} + \mathbf{b}_s)] - \mathbf{b}_0, \quad (27)$$

where (27) represents an update step in the optimization algorithm. It calculates the new value of \mathbf{y}^{k+1} based on the previous value of \mathbf{y}^k , along with the Lagrange multiplier η_s^{k+1} , and the matrices \mathbf{A}_s and \mathbf{b}_s . With (27), it ensures that \mathbf{y}^{k+1} satisfies the optimization problem while considering the impact of the constraint terms represented by \mathbf{A}_s and \mathbf{b}_s .

By further assuming,

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow +\infty} (\mathbf{y}_s^{k+1} - \mathbf{y}_s^k) = 0,$$

we have,

$$\mathbf{A}_0 \mathbf{y}^* + \mathbf{b}_0 + \sum_{s=1}^m \boldsymbol{\mu}_s^* (\mathbf{A}_s \mathbf{y}^* + \mathbf{b}_s) = 0, \quad (28)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\mu}_s^* = \rho \boldsymbol{\mu}_s^{k+1}$ and $k \rightarrow +\infty$ are the corresponding dual variables. Note that (28) is the KKT condition of (16). Therefore, any limit point of $\{\mathbf{y}^k\}$ is a KKT point. ■

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